

CoARA Action Plan 2024-2028

Signed by the President 2025-04-29

CoARA – Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment

- The Coalition started 2022. There are more than 700 members in January 2025.
- KTH joined April 25, 2023, by a decision of the President. The decision to join was prepared by a working group led by the Dean. KTH:s work after the decision has continued in this working group, primarily to develop KTH:s action plan.
 - The action plan is coordinated with CoARA main development and with the initiation and management of the Swedish national chapter. Currently 33 Swedish org has signed, among these are all government research funders and many large universities.
- To KTH the CoARA principles are integral to a desired development where diverse outcomes and practices are recognized among teachers and researchers and addressed as critical to have highest impact of research. KTH emphasizes the need of a qualitative judgement of research.
- The CoARA principles can be, according to KTH, divided into two groups.
 - 1) Principles 1-4 (core principles) addressing the major principles for advancing research assessment and to which KTH should align and steer its development in e.g. recruitment, competence development and quality work.
 - 2) Principles 5-10 addressing the actions and collaborative efforts which should be implemented to fulfill principles 1-4.

The 10 principles and commitments of CoARA

1-4

[CoARA – Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#)

1. Recognize the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research
2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index
4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organizations in research assessment

The 10 principles and commitments of CoARA

5-10

[CoARA – Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#)

5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organizational changes committed to
6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes
7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use
8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition
9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments
10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research

KTH:s reasons for joining CoARA, and which effects that are expected

1. The principles within CoARA stand for a development that KTH acknowledge in terms of how research is evaluated and how merits for researchers and teachers are assessed.
 - Strengthened research culture at KTH that recognizes and rewards quality in all its forms and supports the career development of all staff involved in research. Implemented and developed Quality Assurance System for Research
2. KTH strongly advocate for a joint national development in these matters and recognize opportunities in participating from the start in a national chapter including the Swedish funding landscape, UKÅ as the review authority, and a larger number of higher education institutions who also have signed up.
 - Development at KTH will be aligned with national and international reforms, where KTH is recognized to be influential
3. In parallel, it is critical to KTH to follow and participate in the European and global development of how research assessment will be designed.
 - Established relationships, nationally and internationally, for further knowledge exchange and learning

Additional perspectives for KTH

1. In line with KTH vision *“We take the lead for a sustainable society”* – we need
 - a) a research culture that recognizes and rewards quality in multiple forms,
 - b) a transparent career system inducing progress in research and teaching.

2. Membership of CoARA demonstrates KTH:s dedication to making tangible improvements to research assessment and research culture more broadly.

About the Action plan

- As a member of CoARA, KTH agrees to communicate progress made and exchange good practice with other members of the Coalition. KTH also takes on a systematic approach to work with these issues – partly through the five-year action plan for reformation.
- The President establish the Action plan, the Dean of faculty has the overall responsibility for its deployment and continuously report progress to the President and KTH Management Team.
- KTH is well aligned in the timeline with the other signatories in Sweden regarding the Action plan.
- KTH is engaged in the CoARA National Chapter Sweden that was established in the fall 2024. KTH is involved in four of the five working groups in the National Chapter (see below). The steering committee has a regular dialogue with representatives in the working groups to agree on which aspects KTH prioritizes.
- We will use these working groups to further the work already under way at KTH and drawing on our experiences we are well situated to contribute to their work.

CoARA national chapter working groups,
(*KTH engagement in bold*)

1. **Research applications, individual and research environment support – national level**
2. Good practice in the evaluation of researchers, doctoral education and career paths:
3. **Responsible bibliometrics**
4. **Incentives for open science**
5. **Merit values in collaboration and utilization**

The functions at KTH that primarily involved in the action plan are:

- The Dean and Deputy Dean of the Faculty
- The Faculty council
- The Vice President of Research
- Impact leaders / Deputy heads of Schools
- Management Office, Research Support Office, KTH Library, Communication Department, HR Department
- Assigned members of working groups of The Swedish National Chapter of CoARA

KTH action plan CoARA (2024-2028)

KTH plan a five year development in an iterative manner.

KTH action plan CoARA (2024-2028)

KTH plan a for a continuous interaction with CoARA members and working groups both internationally and nationally.

2024: Prepare and engage

Focus

- Establish a steering committee and develop an action plan
- Raise awareness of research assessment reform at KTH
- Engage with CoARA working groups, national chapter and/or general assembly as appropriate to support systemic reform, exchange good practice and monitor global progress.

Action/results	Responsible	Involved	Milestone
CoARA has been presented in KTH Management Team and in the Faculty Council	Dean of faculty	Management, Faculty Council	June 2024
CoARA principles have been addressed in the investigation of KTH career system	Vice Dean of faculty	Faculty and management	Report October 2024
CoARA principles have been addressed in the revision of KTH quality system for research	Dean of faculty	Working group, management	October-December 2024
Steering committee established: Vice president of research, Library Director, Dean of faculty	Dean of faculty	Administrative officers from Management Office and Research Support Office	November 2024
Participation in national activities	Dean of faculty	Administrative officer Research Support Office	Continuously
Assignment of participants to national working groups	Dean of faculty	From KTH Library, Research Support Office	December 2024
Development of action plan	Dean of faculty	CoARA steering committee , KTH President and KTH Management Group	March 2025

2025: Review and revise

Focus

Gap analysis: KTH career system and CoARA principles as well as KTH quality system and CoARA principles – identify strengths and weaknesses as well as need for change

Clarify KTH:s use of ranking system

Engage with CoARA working groups, national chapter and/or general assembly as appropriate to support systemic reform, exchange good practice and monitor global progress

Action	Responsible	Involved	Milestone
Internal CoARA communication including introduction of CoARA	Dean of faculty	CoARA steering group, CoARA working group, KTH Communication department	March 2025, October 2025 December 2025
Inform and educate Faculty Boards, recruitment committees and promotion committee on CoARA principles	Dean of faculty	KTH Management Office	June 2025
Development of KTH career system	KTH president	Faculty council	July 2025, December 2025
Information to and education of faculty in general and recruitment and promotion boards in specific	Dean of faculty	Faculty council, Faculty boards	December 2025
Revise KTH quality system for research in relation to CoARA principles	Dean of faculty	Faculty council, Faculty boards	October 2025
Clarify ranking practice and impact in relation to CoARA principles, further development of KTH approach and use	Vice President Research	KTH Management Team KTH Management Office, KTH Library	December 2025

2025: Review and revise (continued)

Focus			
Gap analysis: KTH career system and COARA principles as well as KTH quality system and CoARA principles – identify strengths and weaknesses as well as need for change			
Clarify KTH:s use of ranking system			
Engage with CoARA working groups, national chapter and/or general assembly as appropriate to support systemic reform, exchange good practice and monitor global progress			
Action	Responsible	Involved	Milestone
Adopt CoARA principles when evaluating research activities for internal funding.	Vice president research	KTH Library, Research Support Office	Continuously
Further develop Strategic University Intelligence	KTH Management Office	KTH Management group, Faculty Council, Vice president research	June 2025
Implement quality assurance system and quality assessments	Dean of faculty		November 2025

2026: Implement and develop

Focus

Implement reformed procedures with ongoing monitoring

Bibliometric indicators

Communicate progress made via CoARA working groups, national chapter and/or general assembly as appropriate.

Action	Responsible	Involved	Milestone
Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organizational changes committed to	CoARA steering group	Management Team, Impact leaders, Faculty Councils	
Design follow up (business analysis, measurement, follow up)	KTH Management office	Research Support Office Library (KTHB)	
Clarify and develop the use of the bibliometric indicators	Vice president Research	Research Support Office, Impact leaders, KTH Library, KTH Management Team	
Revise CoARA Action Plan	Dean of faculty		March 2026

2027: Demonstrate, follow up and revise

Focus

- Refine reformed procedures where required
- Follow up on progress regarding implementation of CoARA principles
- Further communication of principles and progress in order to strengthen faculty engagement in assessment principles and procedures of research and researchers

Action	Responsible	Involved	Milestone
Follow up reforms, iteration of reformed procedures to implement adjustments and give opportunity for more individuals to engage with procedures.	Dean of faculty	KTH President, KTH Management Team, CoARA steering group	
Communicate internally to staff and students and externally via CoARA working groups, national chapter and/or general assembly as appropriate.	Dean of faculty	Communication department	
Progress report to CoARA in fulfilment of the requirement to report after 5 years of signing.	Dean of faculty	KTH President, KTH Management Team, CoARA steering group	
Undertake actions according to outcome of follow up procedures	KTH President	Faculty Council, KTH Management Team, CoARA steering committee	
Revise CoARA Action Plan	Dean of faculty		March 2027

2028-2029: Evaluate and Evolve

Focus

- Run formal evaluations of reformed procedures
- Develop implementation guidelines for research assessment reform based on the outcomes of reforms achieved in this monitoring period
- Communicate progress made via CoARA working groups, national chapter and/or general assembly as appropriate.

Action	Responsible	Involved	Milestone
Follow up on how Coara's principles have been fulfilled	KTH President	KTH Management Team, Faculty Council	
Follow up on career system	Dean of faculty	Faculty Council	
Development of the quality assurance system and quality assessments	Dean of faculty	Faculty Council	
Participation in national working groups	Dean of faculty	Assigned members of working groups	According to CoARA National chapter
Participation in CoARA working groups and general assembly	Dean of faculty	Assigned members of working groups	According to CoARA
Revise CoARA Action Plan	Dean of faculty		March 2028 + March 2029

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